

A Comparative Study Between the Curricula of English and Comparative Literature

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As a discipline, literature is studied and taught mostly based on languages (like English). Similarly, comparative literature schools have their own right of teaching literature through a specialized curriculum. The purpose of this study is to compare and contrast the curriculums of language-centric schools (in this case, English) and comparative literature schools. Furthermore, this research will demonstrate the fundamental variations in the curricula of selected English and Comparative Literature schools in Bangladesh, India, the United Kingdom, and the United States. The content analysis approach will be used to unearth the distinctions between the selected schools.

Keywords: Literature, Comparative literature, Curricula, Content Analysis.